

Synthesis of some 1-[5'-(Substituted-phenoxy)methyl]-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl]-4-substituted-2-azetidinones as Potential Fungicides

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Several 1-(5'-substituted-phenyl-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl)-3-chloro-4-substituted-2-azetidinones have been synthesised by the annulation of acid chlorides on anils using Et₃N, and their antifungal activities have been reported. Based on screening data attempt has been made to throw light on structure-activity relationship.

THE antibacterial properties of the compounds incorporating a 2-azetidinone ring are well documented¹. However, no attempt has apparently been made to study their antifungal activities. In an attempt to explore this possibility and with a view to obtain compounds of enhanced antifungal properties, we thought it of interest to combine a 2-azetidinone structure with a thiadiazol ring system, the biological versatility of which is well known. With this objective the synthesis and evaluation of antifungal activities of the title compounds were undertaken. The 2-azetidinones have been synthesised by annulation of acetyl chloride on Schiff base in presence of triethylamine in dioxane.

The importance of N-C-S linkage as the possible toxophore in many well known organic sulphur pesticides, such as dithiocarbamates, tetramethylthiourea, disulphide isothiocyanates, thioureas, thiosemicarbazides and mercaptothiadiazoles have been well stressed². If examined from this point of view, a 1,3,4-thiadiazole moiety present in the title compounds have N-C-S linkage and thiosemicarbazide linkage. Thus it was thought that the combination of 1,3,4-thiadiazole system having herbicidal aryloxy moiety³ at position-4 with 2-azetidinone might give the compound of better biological activities. With this objective in mind, such compounds have been synthesised. The authenticity of the products was established by tlc, m.p., m.m.p., pmr and ir spectral data.

The pmr spectra show *cis*-orientation of C₃ and C₄ protons of 2-azetidinones ring in the azetidinones (3). The ir spectra of 3 indicate the presence of β-lactam C=O peaks around 1620-1720 cm⁻¹. The Schiff bases (2) were prepared by refluxing aromatic aldehydes and 2-amino-5-aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles in methanol using glacial acetic acid as catalyst. The requisite 2-amino-5-(aryloxymethyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles have been prepared by oxidative cyclisation of 4-aryloxyacetothiosemicarbazide with H₂SO₄ and ammonia.

- 4a ; R=2,4-(CH₃)₂, R'=C₆H₅
 4b ; R=2-Cl, R'=C₆H₅
 4c ; R=4-Cl, R'=C₆H₅
 4d ; R=4-Cl, 3-CH₃, R'=C₆H₅
 4e ; R=4-Cl, 3-OH, R'=C₆H₅.Cl-*p*
 4f ; R=2-Cl, R'=C₆H₅.Cl-*p*
 4g ; R=4-Cl, R'=C₆H₅.Cl-*p*
 4h ; R=2,4-(CH₃)₂, R'=C₆H₅.Cl-*p*
 4i ; R=4-Cl, R'=C₆H₅.OOH₂-*p*
 4j ; R=2,4-(CH₃)₂, R'=C₆H₅.OOCH₃-*p*

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF VARIOUS 1-[(5'-SUBSTITUTED-PHENOXYMETHYL)-1,3,4-THIADIAZOLE-2'-YL]-4-SUBSTITUTED-2-AZETIDINONES

Compd. no.	M.p.	Yield	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		$\nu_{\max}$ cm^{-1}	δ
				N	S		
3a	205	70.2	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}$	11.46 (11.50)	8.45 (8.76)	1 625 (C=O), 1 560 (Ar ring)	2.00 and 2.20 (6H, d, 2-OH ₂), 3.40–3.70 (2H, m, CH ₂), 4.5 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 5.20 (1H, s, OH), 6.55–7.00 (8H, m, ArH)
3b	174	56.4	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$	11.15 (11.30)	8.50 (8.61)	1 680 (C=O), 1 605 (C=N)	2.15 (2H, s, CH ₂), 4.60 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 5.40 (1H, s, OH), 6.80–7.30 (8H, m, ArH)
3c	142	64.5	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$	11.26 (11.30)	8.52 (8.61)	1 680 (C=O) 1 605 (C=N)	2.10 (2H, s, CH ₂), 4.60 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 5.40 (1H, s, OH), 6.80–7.30 (OH, m, ArH)
3d	208	71.0	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$	10.76 (10.89)	8.37 (8.34)	1 680 (C=O), 1 640 (C=N)	2.20 (3H, s, CH ₃), 4.60 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 5.40 (1H, s, OH), 6.80–7.30 (8H, m, ArH)
3e	194	68.2	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{SCl}_2$	10.10 (10.00)	7.21 (7.44)	1 720 (C=O), 1 640 (C=N)	2.25 (2H, s, CH ₂), 4.30 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 5.60 (1H, s, OH), 6.50–7.20 (7H, m, ArH)
3f	168	62.6	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$	10.21 (10.34)	7.78 (7.88)	1 660 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N)	4.65 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 5.60 (1H, s, OH), 6.45–7.45 (6H, m, ArH)
3g	114–16	67.6	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{SCl}_2$	10.13 (10.34)	7.67 (7.88)	1 680 (C=O), 1 640 (C=N)	2.20 (2H, s, CH ₂), 4.60 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 5.4 (1H, s, OH), 6.80–7.35 (8H, m, ArH)
3h	178	71.7	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$	10.32 (10.51)	7.88 (8.01)	1 720 (C=O), 1 640 (C=N)	2.00 and 2.20 (6H, d, 2-OH ₂), 2.80 (2H, s, CH ₂), 4.50 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 5.40 (1H, s, OH), 6.70–7.00 (7H, m, ArH)
3i	150	72.5	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$	10.19 (10.46)	7.67 (7.97)	1 720 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N)	2.15 (6H, s, 2-OH ₂), 4.40 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.40 (1H, s, OH), 6.80–7.20 (7H, m, ArH)
3j	166–67	79.2	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}$	10.54 (10.63)	7.92 (8.10)	1 720 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N)	2.15 (6H, s, 2-OH ₂), 2.90 (2H, m, CH ₂), 3.30 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 4.50 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.30 (1H, s, OH), 6.50–7.20 (7H, m, ArH)

determined on a Perkin–Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and the nmr spectra (DMSO) on a Varian EM 390 (90 MHz) instrument.

The physical and spectral data of the compounds (3) are presented in Table 1.

2-Amino-5-(aryloxymethyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles: The compounds were prepared according to the reported method⁴. 4-Aryloxyacetothiosemicarbazide (0.1 mol) was treated with concentrated H₂SO₄ (6.5 ml), and the mixture was then cooled and poured into water. The product separating after neutralisation with ammonia was filtered and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol.

1-[5'-Substituted-phenoxyethyl]-1,3,4-thiadiazole-2-yl]-4-substituted-2-azetidinones: A mixture of 2-amino-5-(aryloxymethyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (0.1 mol) and triethylamine (0.2 mol) was dissolved in dioxane (50 ml) and cooled. To this cooled solution, acetyl chloride (0.1 mol) was added slowly at 0° and the mixture was stirred for 24 h and then set aside 48 h at room temperature. The precipitated amine hydrochloride was filtered off and dioxane removed. The residue was poured into water and the resulting solid mass was suction-

filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from chloroform–hexane (20 : 80).

Antifungal activity: All the compounds were evaluated for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *A. flavus* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* at three concentrations, i.e. 10, 100 and 1000 ppm by agar-growth technique. The number of replication in each case was three. The results were compared with the commercial fungicide Bavistin (carbendazin). The percentage inhibition has been calculated by the formula,

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{(C - T)}{C} \times 100$$

where C and T are diameters (mm) of fungus colony in control and in treated plate, respectively. The results are recorded in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The fungicidal data indicate that all the compounds under are moderately toxic to the test fungi at 10 ppm. Their toxicity increases considerably at 100 and 1000 ppm (except compd. h). The presence of thiadiazole moiety at position-1 of the

TABLE 2—FUNGICIDAL ACTIVITIES OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Average % inhibition after 168 h								
	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>			<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>			<i>Helminthosporium oryzae</i>		
	1000	100	10	1000	100	10	1000	100	10
a	91.8	78.5	65.8	92.7	80.7	66.3	40.5	35.0	27.0
b	90.6	85.5	78.6	98.5	96.5	74.3	55.7	44.0	32.6
c	17.6	27.6	41.1	95.3	65.0	30.0	80.3	68.5	55.5
d	95.5	76.3	65.5	91.3	81.8	71.5	36.5	22.7	17.0
e	81.3	65.3	55.7	98.5	94.3	85.6	45.5	32.7	28.5
f	93.7	68.5	60.7	97.6	91.3	78.6	36.5	32.0	31.0
g	85.3	76.5	65.3	81.3	60.3	55.6	67.8	57.5	47.3
h	00.0	00.0	00.0	40.3	25.0	20.0	45.6	32.8	28.5
i	93.8	82.7	78.6	93.6	87.5	81.5	49.5	37.0	31.0
j	78.5	48.7	26.5	91.0	75.3	45.5	75.6	65.4	40.5
Carbendazim	97.5	86.5	81.5	98.6	88.7	81.8	94.1	80.2	78.9

azetidinone ring increases the toxicity to all the species of fungi. The compounds a, b, d, f and i have activities quite comparable to commercial fungicide carbendazim tested under similar condition. The toxicity depends upon the nature and position of the substituents in aryloxy moiety on thiadiazole ring. Substituents at position-2 and -4 on aryloxy moiety appears to induce more fungitoxicity than substituent at position-3 of the same ring. The substitution of OCH₃ group at position-4 of the phenyl ring of the azetidinone ring diminishes fungitoxicity.

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